

A Laser Flash Photolysis Study of Sydnone Triplets. Photophysical Behaviours and Singlet Oxygen Sensitisation†

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Under energy transfer sensitisation in fluid solutions, sydnones form triplets ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^T = 380-400 \text{ nm}$) characterised by short lifetimes ($0.2-2 \mu\text{s}$). From kinetic studies using these compounds as triplet donors and acceptors, their triplet energies are estimated at $41-47 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. Based on the lack of any residual absorbance change following the decay of triplets, it is claimed that they are not involved as precursors in the phototransformation of sydnones to nitrilimines. The oxygen quenching of sydnone triplets occurs predominantly by the energy transfer mechanism producing singlet oxygen in nearly quantitative yields.

SUBJECT of many steady-state photochemical studies¹⁻⁷, sydnones (1,2,3-oxadiazol-5-ones) undergo facile photoelimination of carbon dioxide producing nitrilimines (Scheme 1). Only very

lysis, we have investigated the spectral and kinetic behaviours of the triplets of a number of sydnones (Chart 1). It is shown that though short-lived,

Scheme 1

- (1) $R^1 = R^2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
- (2) $R^1 = p\text{-OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $R^2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
- (3) $R^1 = \text{OH}_2$, $R^2 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$
- (4) $R^1 = p\text{-OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $R^2 = \text{OH}_2$
- (5) $R^1 = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $R^2 = \text{H}$
- (6) $R^1 = p\text{-OH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $R^2 = \text{H}$

Chart 1

limited information is available regarding the nature of the excited states participating in this photoreaction or the details of bond reorganisation leading to the overall transformation. The excited state properties of sydnones assume special significance because of their 'meso-ionic' nature⁸ in the ground state. Although, for several related systems, the triplets of metastable zwitterionic species have been implicated⁹ as distinct entities in the course of ring closures along triplet routes; to the best of our knowledge, no attempt has been made to characterise triplets directly photogenerated from stable dipolar substrates.

Employing time-resolved techniques, based on nanosecond laser flash photolysis and pulse radio-

these triplets do not undergo CO_2 elimination to nitrilimines. In view of the reactivity⁷ of sydnones with singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$, $^1\Delta_g$), the interaction of their triplets with ground-state oxygen ($^3\text{O}_2$, $^3\Sigma_g^-$) is of interest; in the latter case, one may expect direct 1,3-addition (spin-allowed) to compete favourably with energy transfer leading to $^1\text{O}_2$. In order to throw light on this aspect, we have measured the efficiency of $^1\text{O}_2$ production in the course of the quenching of sydnone triplets by $^3\text{O}_2$.

Experimental

The preparation of sydnones 1-6 (Chart 1) was carried out by literature methods referred to in earlier publications⁶⁻⁸. Benzene and acetonitrile,

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both from Aldrich, were of spectral grades. *N*-Methylthioacridone (NMTA) was prepared from *N*-methylacridone according to the procedure available in the literature^{10,11}. Thiocoumarin was obtained as a gift (from Professor V. Ramamurthy). The other compounds and reagents used in this work were of best grades commercially available, and were purified by recrystallisation or by distillation under reduced pressure.

The ground-state absorption spectra were recorded in a Cary 219 spectrophotometer (1 nm band-pass). For laser flash photolysis, use was made of outputs from a Quanta-Ray Nd-YAG system coupled with a Quanta-Ray PDL-1 dye laser unit. The laser pulse excitation was carried out at 355 (third harmonic), 425 (stilbene 420 in methanol pumped at 355 nm) or 485 nm (coumarin 480 in methanol pumped at 355 nm); the intensities of the pulses (~6 ns) were kept in the range 4-10 mJ. The details of the kinetic spectrophotometer and the data collection system are given in previous publication^{12,13}. The pulse radiolysis experiments were performed, employing 7 MeV electron pulses (5 ns) from Notre Dame ARCO-LP-7 linear accelerator; further details are available elsewhere¹⁴. Except for oxygen quenching, the solutions for both laser photolysis and pulse radiolysis were deoxygenated by bubbling high-purity argon through them (10-15 min).

Results

Quenching of sensitiser triplets by sydnones: Under direct laser excitation, none of the sydnones under study produces transients having properties characteristic of a triplet (see later). Thus, we took resort to the energy transfer sensitisation method for generating the triplets. For this purpose, it was necessary to know the approximate location of

triplet energies (E_T) of these molecules. Since practically no phosphorescence is observed for the sydnones in glassy matrices at 77 K, their E_T 's were estimated¹⁵ in fluid solutions by measuring the rate constants (k_q^T) for the quenching of a series of sensitiser triplets with varying E_T 's in the range 41-69 kcal mol⁻¹. Sydnones **1**, **3** and **5** were used as representative quenchers. k_q^T 's were obtained from the linear plots based on the equation,

$$k_{\text{obsd}}^T = k_o^T + k_q^T [\text{sydnone}]$$

where, k_{obsd}^T is the pseudo-first order rate constant for the decay of a sensitiser triplet and k_o^T is the rate constant for its decay in the absence of a quencher. Except for tris(bipyridine)ruthenium(II) complex, the sensitiser triplets were monitored by transient absorptions in benzene at or near the maxima at 460-700 nm; at these long wavelengths, absorptions due to the sydnone triplets (*i.e.* products of energy transfer) were small (see later). The triplet decay kinetics in the case of the Ru^{II} complex in acetonitrile was followed in terms of its phosphorescence emission at 630 nm. In experiments where the sensitiser triplets were produced by direct laser excitation at 355 nm, the sydnone quenchers, particularly **1** at relatively high concentrations (1-2 mM), absorbed a significant fraction of laser photons; however, this was not a serious problem because the direct excitation of sydnones did not produce any transients having serious spectral or temporal overlap with the sensitiser triplet.

The data concerning k_q^T are presented in Table 1. In spite of some fluctuations in k_q^T 's their trends with respect to sensitiser E_T 's suggest fall-off regions at $E_T = 41-47$ kcal mol⁻¹. In particular, k_q^T 's for benz[*a*]anthracene ($E_T = 47$ kcal mol⁻¹) and pyrene-1-aldehyde ($E_T \sim 45$ kcal mol⁻¹) indicate that while the triplet energy of sydnone **1** is lower than that of the aldehyde, that of **3** as well as **5** is slightly

TABLE 1—BIMOLECULAR RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE QUENCHING OF SENSITISER TRIPLETS BY SYDNONES IN BENZENE AT 296 K

Sensitiser	E_T^a cal mol ⁻¹	Laser excitation wavelength nm	Monitoring wavelength nm	k_q^T , 10 ⁹ M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹		
				1	3	5
Benzophenone	69	355	532	4.9	4.6	6.1
Phenanthrene ^b	62	355	490	4.8	5.2	6.4
Chrysenes ^b	57	355	590	5.1	5.2	6.3
Fluorenone	53	425	645	2.9	5.1	3.7
Camphorquinone	52	485	700	2.6	5.2	2.8
Thiocoumarin	51	425	485	6.3	3.0	6.6
tris(Bipyridine) Ru ^{II} ^d	48	485	630	2.4	0.8	1.2
Benz[<i>a</i>]anthracene ^b	47	355	490	4.0	3.2	4.4
Pyrene-1-aldehyde	~45	425	460	2.7	~0.6	≤0.1
<i>N</i> -Methylthioacridone ^c	45	485	520	3.6	1.1	4.1
9,10-Diphenylanthracene ^f	41	485	460	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1

^a Ref. 22; S. L. Murov, "Handbook of Photochemistry", Marcel-Dekker, New York, 1973; H. Gerner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, 86, 2629; C. V. Kumar, S. K. Chattopadhyay and P. K. Das, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1983, 38, 141; S. K. Chattopadhyay, C. V. Kumar and P. K. Das, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1983, 98, 250; T. R. Evans and P. A. Leermakers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 4380.
^b ±15%. ^c Benzene containing 5% ethyl iodide was used for these aromatic hydrocarbons. ^d Phosphorescence was monitored for the complex in acetonitrile. ^e k_q^T 's for NMTA triplet quenching by the other three sydnones are 3.8, 2.7 and 4.0 × 10⁹ M⁻¹ s⁻¹ for **2**, **4** and **6**, respectively. ^f The triplet of 9,10-diphenylanthracene was produced *via* sensitisation by NMTA triplet ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 485$ nm) in a solution saturated with the anthracene.

higher (i.e. at 45-47 kcal mol⁻¹). From the onsets of the lowest-energy absorption band-systems of sydnone in benzene (~ 400 nm for 1 and 2 and ~ 370 nm for 3-6), their lowest singlet excited states, as seen in absorption, are estimated at 71 and 77 kcal mol⁻¹ for 1-2 and 3-6, respectively. Since the singlet-triplet energy separation¹⁸ for a π, π^* state is typically of the order of 30 kcal mol⁻¹, E_T's of sydnone suggested by k₀T's in Table 1 and by their ground-state absorption spectra are consistent with one another.

Triplet absorption spectra and decay kinetics : It is evident from the data in Table 1 that the triplets of camphorquinone (CQ; E_T=52 kcal mol⁻¹) and thiocoumarin (E_T=51 kcal mol⁻¹) possess sufficiently high energies for exothermic excitation transfer to the sydnone. More importantly, these two sensitizers can be excited at laser wavelengths in the visible (specifically, 485 and 425 nm, respectively) where the sydnone do not absorb, thus permitting the use of high concentrations (20-50 mM) of the latter. Upon laser flash photolysis of CQ or thiocoumarin in the presence of sydnone, short-lived transients are observed. As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, these transients absorb primarily in the spectral region 380-450 nm and decay by clean first order kinetics. Similar transient absorption phenomena are also observed in the course of the pulse

Fig. 1. Triplet-triplet absorption spectra of (A) 1, (B) 2 and (C) 3 in benzene. The triplets were produced by sensitisation by ³CQ* (λ_{ex}=485 nm) in the presence of 20-30 mM sydnone. The insets show typical kinetic traces for triplet decay at or near the absorption maxima: (a) 1, (b) 2 and (c) 3.

Fig. 2. Triplet-triplet absorption spectra of (A) 4, (B) 5 and (C) 6 in benzene. These were observed under sensitisation by ³CQ* (λ_{ex}=485 nm) in the presence of 20-30 mM sydnone. Representative kinetic traces for triplet decay are shown in the insets: (a) 4, (b) 5 and (c) 6.

radiolysis¹⁷ of 0.1 M biphenyl in the presence of 5-10 mM sydnone in benzene. In these experiments, biphenyl triplets (E_T=66 kcal mol⁻¹), initially produced by energy transfer from pulse radiolytic solvent triplets, sensitise the formation of sydnone triplets (see equations 1-3, Bz ≡ benzene, Bp ≡ biphenyl and S ≡ sydnone). A few representative transient spectra are shown in Fig. 3.

The assignment of the observed transients as sydnone triplets is based on the following facts. First, they are formed under conditions in which triplet energy transfer to sydnone is feasible. Second, they are quenched by typical triplet quenchers, namely, oxygen, di-*tert*-butylnitroxy radical and ferrocene (see later). Third, when they are generated in the presence of ~ 0.5 mM *all-trans*-1,6-diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene (E_T=34 kcal mol⁻¹), relatively slow formation of the triplet of the latter with characteristic, intense absorption spectrum at 400-450 nm (λ_{max}^T=426 nm in benzene) is noted;

Fig. 3. Transient absorption spectra of the triplets of (A) 1, (B) 2 and (C) 5 produced via sensitisation by pulse-radiolytic biphenyl triplet in benzene.

this establishes the triplet sensitising capability of the observed transients from sydnones.

Assuming that the quenching of ${}^3\text{CQ}^*$ by sydnones occurs entirely by energy transfer, we have determined their triplet-triplet extinction coefficients using the comparative technique. In this, the end-of-pulse absorbance change (ΔA_{CO}^T) due to ${}^3\text{CQ}^*$ at 700 nm in the absence of a quencher is compared with that (ΔA_{S}^T) due to ${}^3\text{S}^*$ at 380-410 nm produced in the presence of high [S] so that the decay of ${}^3\text{CQ}^*$ occurs essentially by energy transfer to S (that is $k_q^T[\text{S}] \gg k_o^T$, see equations 4 and 5). Equation (6) was used to calculate sydnone triplet extinction coefficients (ϵ_{S}^T). For ϵ_{CO}^T at 700 nm, a

$$\epsilon_{\text{S}}^T = \epsilon_{\text{CO}}^T \cdot \frac{\Delta A_{\text{S}}^T}{\Delta A_{\text{CO}}^T} \quad (6)$$

value of $900 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was used (as determined by the comparative method in which anthracene, $\epsilon^T = 4.5 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 428 nm in benzene, was used as the acceptor). The triplet spectral data (λ_{max}^T and ϵ_{max}^T) and lifetimes (τ_T) for sydnones are summarised in Table 2.

It is noted (Table 1) that the sydnones quench *N*-methylthioacridone (NMTA) triplet ($E_T = 43 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) with rate constants significantly higher than those expected from the trends for the other sensitizers. For example, energy transfer from ${}^3\text{NMTA}^*$ to sydnone 5 would be endothermic although k_q^T in this case is close to the limit of diffusion control. In order to throw some light on the quenching mechanism, the efficiency (ϕ_{ET}) of energy transfer was obtained based on equation (7),

$$\phi_{\text{ET}} = \frac{\Delta A_{\text{S}}^T}{\Delta A_{\text{NMTA}}^T} \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{\text{NMTA}}^T}{\epsilon_{\text{S}}^T} \quad (7)$$

where, ΔA^T 's are end-of-pulse triplet absorbance changes due to ${}^3\text{NMTA}^*$ at 520 nm (measured by 485 nm laser excitation of NMTA in the absence of a sydnone) and due to ${}^3\text{S}^*$ at 380-410 nm (measured by excitation of NMTA in the presence of $\sim 50 \text{ mM}$ sydnone) and ϵ^T 's are the corresponding T-T extinction coefficients. The value¹¹ of $9.3 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was used for ϵ_{NMTA}^T . The ϕ_{ET} data given in Table 2 suggest interaction(s) other than energy transfer to be operative in the case of 3-6. It should also be noted that the absorbance changes in the region (400-490 nm) of NMTA ground-state absorption following the decay of transients (${}^3\text{S}^*$) show practically no permanent loss of the thioketone.

Quenching of sydnone triplets: The bimolecular rate constants (k_q^T) for the quenching of sydnone triplets by oxygen, di-*tert*-butylnitroxy (DTBN, stable free radical) and ferrocene were obtained by measuring the observed rate constant (k_{obs}^T) for

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL AND KINETIC PROPERTIES OF SYDNONE TRIPLETS IN BENZENE AT 296 K

Sydnone	λ_{max}^T ^a	ϵ_{max}^T ^b	τ_T ^c	$\phi_{\text{ET}}^{\text{d,e}}$	$k_q^T, 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ^e			ϕ_{Δ}^T
					O ₂	DTBN	Ferrocene	
1	≤ 400	6.8	1.2	1.0	2.0	0.061	1.6	0.78
2	≤ 400	6.4	1.0	1.0	1.9	0.039	1.6	0.88
3	400	7.8	0.22	0.57	1.8	0.052	2.3	
4	400	2.0	1.8	0.16	1.7	0.078	5.1	
5	380	1.4	2.0	0.19	1.9	0.16	6.7	0.80
6	380	1.7	2.3	0.88	1.8	0.12	5.7	0.88

^a $\pm 5 \text{ nm}$. ^b $\pm 20\%$. ^c $\pm 15\%$. ^d ϕ_{ET} denotes the efficiency of energy transfer in the quenching of NMTA triplet by sydnones (see text). ^e $\pm 20\%$

the enhanced decay of their transient absorption (380-410 nm) as a function of quencher concentration. A few plots based on $k_{\text{obs}}^T = \tau^{-1} + k_q^T[Q]$ with ferrocene as the quencher are presented in Fig. 4. The k_q^T data are given in Table 2. Attempts to quench the triplets of 2, 3 and 5 by dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate (dipolarophile) and 2,5-dimethyl-2,4-hexadiene proved unrewarding ($k_q^T \leq 1.5 \times 10^6 M^{-1} s^{-1}$). Also, azulene was found to be a poor quencher for the triplets of 1 and 2 ($k_q^T < 10^9 M^{-1} s^{-1}$).

Fig. 4. Plots for the quenching of sydnone triplets by ferrocene: (A) 1, (B) 2, (C) 3 and (D) 6.

Efficiency of singlet oxygen sensitisation by sydnone triplets: With 1, 2, 5 and 6, the fractions (ϕ_{Δ}^T) of sydnone triplets (quenched by 1O_2) that lead to 1O_2 formation were measured. Two methods based on CQ and NMTA as the triplet sensitisers respectively were used under 485 nm laser excitation. For both, diphenylisobenzofuran (DPBF) was employed as 1O_2 monitor. The various steps leading to 1O_2 formation are as follows (Sens $\equiv$ sensitiser, i.e. CQ or NMTA, and D $\equiv$ DPBF).

The method based on NMTA as the sensitiser was applied to 1 and 2, since ϕ_{ET} in these cases were

unity (Table 2). Solutions of NMTA in aerated benzene (absorbance=0.1 at 485 nm in 2 mm cell) containing 0.05 mM DPBF and varying concentrations of sydneses (0.0-5.0 mM) were flash photolysed at 485 nm and the negative absorbance changes (ΔA^D) due to DPBF ground-state depletion (equation 14) measured at 420 nm. From the dependence of ΔA^D on $[S]$, it was possible to calculate ϕ_{Δ}^T for $^3S^*$ with respect to that for $^3\text{NMTA}^*$. The details of the method are given elsewhere¹⁹. The method based on CQ as the sensitiser was applied to 4 and 5 and required using high concentrations of sydneses so that $^3\text{CQ}^*$ was quenched entirely by energy transfer to them (may be noted that $^3\text{CQ}^*$ is quite long-lived even in aerated benzene, $\tau_T = 2.2 \mu s$). It was important that 4 and 5 in the ground-state were poor reactants¹⁹ for $^1O_2^*$. Comparison of absorbance change (ΔA_{CQ}^T) due to $^3\text{CQ}^*$ at 700 nm in the absence of DPBF and sydnone with that due to DPBF bleaching at 420 nm observed in the presence of 0.05 mM DPBF and 10-30 mM sydnone led to the measurement of ϕ_{Δ}^T . Use was made of equation (15),

$$\phi_{\Delta}^T = \frac{\Delta A^D}{\Delta A_{\text{CQ}}^T} \cdot \frac{e_{\text{CQ}}^T}{e^D} \cdot \frac{k_{11} + k_{12} [^3O_2]}{k_{13} [^3O_2]} \cdot \frac{k_{23} + k_{14} [D]}{k_{14} [D]} \quad (15)$$

where, the rate constants k_{11} , k_{12} and k_{14} refer to equations (11), (13) and (14), respectively and k_{13} represents the overall rate constant for sydnone triplet quenching by oxygen (equations 12a-c). k_{11} and k_{12} are the rate parameters measured in the present study (Table 2) and the values for k_{13} and k_{14} are available in the literature²⁰. ϕ_{Δ}^T data (Table 2) obtained by the two methods suggest that the sydnone triplet quenching by oxygen is dominated by energy transfer (equation 12a).

Discussion

Direct laser flash photolysis of sydneses 1 and 2 in benzene or methanol and 4-6 in methanol, produces long-lived transients ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 360-380$ nm and τ 's $> 100 \mu s$), characterised by oxygen-insensitive decay kinetics. These are best assigned as nitrilimines, spectral and kinetic behaviors of which will be described elsewhere. The decay of the sydnone triplets observed in the present study does not lead to any significant residual absorption attributable to nitrilimines. Thus, the phototransformation of sydneses to nitrilimines (Scheme 1) appears to be a reaction originating from the singlet state. Also, under 485 nm laser excitation of CQ in the presence of 0.5-1 mM sydneses, practically no depletion in the region of their ground-state absorption (320-340 nm) results from the triplet decay; this suggests that photochemistry in the lowest triplet state of sydneses is negligible. Our findings differ sharply with the conclusions reached by Huseya *et al.*⁴ for 3-cyclohexyl-4-phenylsydnone. Based on the marked quenching effect of 1,3-pentadiene on the photochemical reaction of 3-cyclohexyl-4-phenylsydnone,

the triplet state has been implicated as photoreactive for this system.

The k_q^T data (Table 2) with ferrocene ($E_T \sim 39$ kcal mol⁻¹) as the quencher give semiquantitative estimates for the energies of relaxed triplets of the sydrones at ≥ 40 kcal mol⁻¹. For 4-6, k_q^T 's are in the limit of diffusion-control and hence the relaxed triplet energies for these systems should be higher than E_T of ferrocene by at least 2-3 kcal mol⁻¹. A comparison of these estimates with E_T 's arrived at from k_q^T 's for the quenching of sensitizer triplets by sydrones (Table 1) points out that there is no substantial structural relaxation in the lowest triplet state of sydrones following their photoexcitation. This is not surprising in view of the geometric constraint and rigidity imposed by the five-membered ring.

It seems plausible that the decay of sydnone triplets represents nearly vertical inter-system crossing from a biradicaloid triplet configuration 7 to the ground-state zwitterionic configuration. It is of interest to examine how the substituents at 3- and 4-positions affect the inter-system crossing rates. The lifetime (τ_1) data in Table 2 reveal the

following trend : 5, 6 > 1, 2, 4 > 3. Thus, while the substitution of an aryl or an alkyl group at the 4-position results in the shortening of τ_T , the aryl substitution at the 3-position makes τ_T longer. It seems that an aryl or an alkyl group at the 4-position stabilises a radical center at this position (biradicaloid structure 8) and hence decreases the average distance between the two unpaired electrons. The latter in turn favours spin-orbit coupling²¹ for inter-system crossing. On the other hand, an aryl group at the 3-position makes the lone pair of electrons on the nitrogen atom less available for mediating inter-system crossing. Hence, τ_T increases on going from 3 to 1 or 2.

The efficiency of energy transfer (ϕ_{ET}) in the course of the quenching of NMTA triplet ($E_T = 43$ kcal mol⁻¹)²² by a sydnone is determined by the relative location of the triplet energy of the latter with respect to NMTA; that is, by the exothermicity of the energy transfer process. Specifically, with 4-6 as quenchers, the energy transfer is decisively endothermic and, although the k_q^T 's are high, a major portion of the quenching takes place by a non-energy-transfer mechanism. Since no loss of NMTA occurs as a result of the interaction, a permanent dipolarophilic 1,3-addition of the thioetone triplet to sydrones is ruled out. In analogy to the mechanism of quenching of thioetone triplets by olefins, the formation of an unstable diradical that reverts to ground states, may be invoked in the

course of the interaction of ³NMTA* and sydrones. This is shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The rate constants for the quenching of sydnone triplets by oxygen are all close to $1/9 k_{airr}$, where k_{airr} is the rate constant for a fully diffusion-controlled process. This conforms to mechanism(s) of oxygen quenching in which the singlet configuration of the encounter complex between oxygen

and the triplet substrate plays the major role (equation 16a). The nearly quantitative efficiencies of ¹O₂* photosensitisation (Table 2) point out to the dominance of energy transfer. Permanent 1,3-addition of ³O₂ to ³S*, though spin-allowed, appears to be a negligible process (quantum efficiency < 20%) compared to the energy transfer. This is supported by the fact that within our experimental errors, we do not observe any significant depletion of sydnone ground state absorption following the oxygen quenching of their triplets (sensitized by ³CO* or ³NMTA* in air-saturated benzene).

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